

A POTENTIOMETRIC STUDY OF THE CONSTITUTION OF THIOCARBAMIDE AND PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDE

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Various formulae have been proposed for thiocarbamide and its derivatives :

Potentiometric work embodied in this note establishes the acidic nature of the thiocarbamide and its derivatives in aqueous solution supporting partly the configuration (1).

A weak solution of phenylthiocarbamide was titrated potentiometrically with a weak solution of caustic soda.

The graphs (A) and (B) corresponding to the readings show two step-like bends. These correspond to two dissociation constants p_{k1} and p_{k2} : thiocarbamide 7.189, 7.381 ; phenylthiocarbamide 6.865, 7.189 establishing the dibasic nature of these substances.

Fig. 1
(curve A)

Aq. phenylthiocarbamide soln. at 37°.

Fig. 2
(curve B)

Aq. thiocarbamide soln. at 37°.

The titrations carried out in aqueous medium show that only 2% of the substance in each case are titratable, *i. e.* 98% are present in some other non-acidic form. Similar titrations in aqueous alcoholic solution resulted in the suppression of this acidity *i. e.* the disappearance of the step-like bends, already referred to.

This behaviour of thiocarbamide and its phenyl derivative opens up two possibilities, either (C), these substances are mixtures of two definite and separate forms or (D), the acidic and non-acidic forms are tautomers in equilibrium. Rejecting (C) it could be said with certainty that these compounds could not be separated into acidic and non-acidic forms. Further work is in progress to clarify the (D).

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